

Studies in the antimicrobial activities of 1-substituted-3-formamidinothiocarbamides and 1,3-bis-(substitutedthioamido)guanidines

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Abstract : The present research work has been undertaken in the synthesis of nitrogen, nitrogen and sulphur containing heteroacycles and heterocycles and to investigate their applications in medicinal, agricultural, industrial, pharmacological and biochemical faculties. Synthesis of novel series of 1-substituted-3-formamidinothiocarbamide and 1,3-bis-(substitutedthioamido)guanidine and study of their antimicrobial activities by MIC method to obtained new series of effective drugs has been presented in this paper.

Keywords : Guanidine derivates, antimicrobial activity.

Thiocarbamido and guanidino compounds find wide applications in pharmacological and other fields of daily life¹.

It was thought interesting to interact guanidine (1) with alkyl/aryl isothiocyanates (2) in carbon tetrachloride and ethanol-acetone mediums to synthesise new series of 1-substituted-3-formamidinothiocarbamides (3) and 1,3-bis-(substitutedthioamido)guanidines (4) respectively (Scheme 1). These drugs may show effective drug effect

in medicinal and agricultural fields, so antimicrobial activities of these newly synthesised drugs were screened against *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. subtilis*, *A. niger*, *C. albicans* pathogens which are hereto not known.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Substituted isothiocyanates were prepared according to literature method².

where, R = phenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, *p*-tolyl, methyl, ethyl, *t*-butyl

Scheme 1

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1-Phenyl-3-formamidinothiocarbamide (3a) :

A mixture of guanidine (0.1 M), phenylisothiocyanate (2a) (0.1 M) and carbon tetrachloride (50 ml) was refluxed on water-bath for 2 h. A product compound gradually separated out. It was filtered hot and dried at room temperature to obtain yellowish needle shape crystals (yield 74%), m.p. 130 °C. The compound is soluble in alcohol, acetone and dioxane. Desulphurised by alkaline plumbite solution. Benzene solution of this compound when treated with pure and dry carbondisulphide, the yellow colour was developed which clearly indicate presence of imino group². The R_f (dioxane) value was found to be 0.31. IR spectra of compound shows $\nu(\text{N-H})$ 3393.6 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C=N})$ 1661.1 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N} > \text{C=S})$ 1101.8 cm^{-1} grouping. The PMR spectra of the compound shows signals due to N-H proton at δ 4.0 ppm, the signal at δ 7.2 ppm is due to Ar-H and signals due to Ar-NH proton at δ 6.1 ppm (Found : C, 48.16; H, 4.03; N, 28.15; S, 15.17. Calcd. : C, 49.48; H, 5.15; N, 28.86; S, 16.49%).

Similarly, other compounds (3b-3f) were synthesised by above mentioned method and enlisted in Table 1.

1,3-Bis-(phenylthioamido)guanidine (4a) :

A mixture of guanidine (0.1 M), phenylisothiocyanate

(0.2 M), ethanol (50 ml) and acetone (50 ml) was refluxed on water-bath for 12 h. A product gradually separated out. It was filtered hot and dried at room temperature to obtain brown colour needle shape crystals (yield 87%), m.p. 182 °C. The compound is soluble in alcohol, dioxane, carbontetrachloride, acetone and benzene. Benzene solution of compound when treated with pure and dry carbondisulphide, the yellow colour was developed which clearly indicate presence of imino group. The R_f (dioxane) value was found to be 0.34. IR spectra of compound shows $\nu(\text{N-H})$ 3387.3 cm^{-1} , $\nu[\text{C-H}(\text{Ar})]$ 3147.7 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C=N})$ 1666.3 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C=NH})$ 1575.9 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C-N})$ 1395.3 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N} > \text{C=S})$ 1178 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C-S})$ 746.9 cm^{-1} grouping. The PMR spectra of the compound shows signals due to Ar-NH protons at δ 7.99-8.0 ppm, Ar-H protons at δ 6.9 ppm, NH protons at δ 3.25-3.27 ppm. Signals at δ 2.55 ppm is due to moisture in DMSO- d_6 and 1.24 is due to DMSO (Found : C, 53.59; H, 3.88; N, 21.05; S, 19.27. Calcd. : C, 54.71; H, 4.56; N, 21.27; S, 19.45%).

Similarly, other compounds (4b-4f) were synthesised by above mentioned method and enlisted in Table 2.

Antimicrobial activities :

The antimicrobial and antifungal activities of all these compounds were studied by MIC process using cup-plate

Table 1. Physical data of the synthesised compounds^a

Compd.	R	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molecular formula
3a	Phenyl	74	130	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ S
3b	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	84	142	C ₈ H ₉ N ₄ SCl
3c	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	69	204	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₄ S
3d	Methyl	72	189	C ₃ H ₈ N ₄ S
3e	Ethyl	59	115	C ₄ H ₁₀ N ₄ S
3f	<i>t</i> -Butyl	67	149	C ₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ S

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis.

Table 2. Physical data of the synthesised compounds^a

Compd.	R	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molecular formula
4a	Phenyl	87	182	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₅ S ₂
4b	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	82	194	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ S ₂ Cl ₂
4c	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	72	189	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ S ₂
4d	Methyl	82	160	C ₅ H ₁₁ N ₅ S ₂
4e	Ethyl	68	172	C ₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ S ₂
4f	<i>t</i> -Butyl	62	169	C ₁₁ H ₂₃ N ₅ S ₂

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis.

Table 3. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of compound

Compd.	Antibacterial activity (nm)					Antifungal activity (nm)	
	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
3a	1.2	0.8	1.2	0.8	1.2	0.8	0.8
3b	1.6	1.0	1.8	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.1
3c	1.4	1.2	1.4	1.0	1.5	1.2	1.0
3d	0.8	0.2	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.2	0.5
3e	1.0	0.5	0.6	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.5
3f	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.8	1.2	0.6	0.8
4a	1.4	1.1	1.4	1.5	1.8	1.5	1.3
4b	2.1	1.4	2.1	1.3	1.5	1.8	1.6
4c	1.8	1.6	1.8	1.2	2.2	2.0	2.1
4d	1.0	1.8	1.2	0.8	1.0	0.8	0.8
4e	1.6	0.8	0.8	0.5	1.5	0.2	0.6
4f	1.4	0.8	0.8	1.0	1.2	0.5	1.0

agar diffusion method. All compounds were screened for their antibacterial activities by using cup-plate agar diffusion method in DMF, using standard Co-Trimazine 25 µg/ml against gram positive and gram negative bacteria such as *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa* and *B. subtilis*. All compounds were also screened for their antifungal activity by using cup-plate agar diffusion method in DMF using standard Griseofulvin (10 µg/ml) against *A. niger* and *C. albicans*.

After the period of inoculation, zones of inhibition were recorded around the wells and the results are cited in Table 3.

All the seven organisms studied are human pathogens. From the results it is clear that all the compounds (except 3a and 3f) showed remarkable and considerable antimicrobial activities.

All the compounds shows highly activities against *S. typhi* (except 3f). As newly synthesised thiocarbamides show remarkable antimicrobial activity, so these compounds can be easily used as alternative for the treatment of diseases caused by *S. typhi* only if they do not have toxic and other side effects after the detail study.

Compounds 3b, 3c, 4a-d shows remarkable antibacterial activities against *E. coli*, compounds 3a-c, 4a-d shows antibacterial activities against *S. aureus*, 3b, 3c, 4a-c and 4f shows antimicrobial activity against *P. aeruginosa*. All the compounds shows remarkable antibacterial activities against *B. subtilis* like *S. typhi*.

Compounds 3b, 3c, 4a-c shows remarkable antifungal activity against *A. niger* while 3b, 3c, 4a-c and 4f

shows against *C. albicans*.

From above data it is clear that these compounds are highly effective against *S. typhi* and *B. subtilis*. So much more study is required on these compounds in biochemical and medicinal direction. It is also conclude that these compounds show remarkable antibacterial activity than antifungal activity.

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References

1. D. T. Tayade, *Oriental J. Chem.*, 1997, 13, 323; M. H. Khan and S. M. Giri, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1975, 64, 1428; J. V. Ram, V. Dobe, A. Ci Pieter and A. J. Vlitineu, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1989, 26, 26; R. S. Sharma and S. C. Bahel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 713; M. Suga, T. Akita, T. Konno and Y. Shiraiwa, *Jap. Pat.* 60, 1989, 233066.
2. A. I. Vogel. "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry including Qualitative Organic Analysis", ELBS and Longman Greek and Co. Ltd., 1954, 615.
3. H. Krall and R. D. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 6.